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Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	5
2. Scope and Structure of the CDP.....	6
3. About FRONTSH1P.....	7
3.1 Overall Objective	7
3.2 Specific Objectives.....	7
3.3 Expected Impact.....	8
4. Communication and Dissemination Overview	10
4.1 Communication Objectives and Messages	10
4.1.1 General Objectives	10
4.1.2 Key Messages	10
4.1.3 Specific Messages per Circular Systemic Solution.....	12
4.2 Target Groups	13
4.2.1 Target Group Segmentation.....	14
4.3 Communication Instruments	18
4.3.1 Tools.....	19
4.3.2 Editorial Plan.....	24
5. Evaluation Methods.....	25
5.1 Monitoring.....	25
5.2 Communication and Dissemination Indicators and Reporting	25
5.3 Communication and Dissemination KPIs.....	27
6. Internal Communication.....	28
6.1 Coordination.....	28
6.2 Workflow	30
6.3 Rights and Obligations	30
7. Visual Identity & Branding	32
7.1 Logo & CSS Branding	32
7.2 Fonts.....	33
7.3 Colours.....	33
7.4 Examples of Visual Identity and Branding	35

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Target Groups.....	14
Figure 2: Project Logos	32
Figure 3: CSSs' Colour Branding	32
Figure 4: Logos' Colour Codes.....	33
Figure 5: CSSs' Colour Codes	34
Figure 6: PPT Template Title Slide.....	35
Figure 7: Brandbook Extract.....	35
Table 1: Target Groups	13
Table 2: Communication and Dissemination KPIs.....	27
Table 3: Communication and Dissemination Coordination	29

List of Abbreviations

CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CCS	Clusters Collaboration Secretariat
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CDS	Communication and Dissemination Secretariat
CSS	Circular Systemic Solution
DRT	Dissemination and Replication Team
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information Communications and Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This document is deliverable 9.1 and presents the overall communication and dissemination strategy to be applied for the Horizon 2020 project FRONTSH1P – A FRONTrunner approach to Systemic circular, Holistic & Inclusive solutions for a new Paradigm of territorial circular economy.

FRONTSH1P project began on 1 November 2021 and will continue for 48 months. FRONTSH1P is centred in the Polish region of Łódzkie and contributes to further the green and just transition of the region away from its current linear model of economic development, towards the region's decarbonisation and territorial regeneration. It does so by demonstrating four circular systemic solutions (CSSs). Each CSS will be implemented in the region and targets an economic sector that is itself aiming towards decarbonisation: Wood Packaging, Food & Feed, Water & Nutrients, and Plastic & Rubber Waste. Another major goal in the demonstration of the CSSs is their replicability. A feat that will be proven during the project by their implementation in four other European regions: Campania (Italy), Stereá Elláda (Greece), Região do Norte (Portugal), and Friesland (the Netherlands). FRONTSH1P will apply a circular governance model and create circular regional clusters, which will involve a wide range of local, regional, and national stakeholders, both from the public and private sphere.

This document contains general information on the FRONTSH1P project and outlines the communication and dissemination activities to be undertaken during the four years of the project. It comprises information on FRONTSH1P's objectives and expected impact, as well as a presentation of the communication and dissemination activities planned and undertaken. It provides an overview of the project's key messages, target group segmentation and communication instruments. Furthermore, it explains the designated evaluation and monitoring methods, elaborates on internal communication measures, and illustrates the project's visual identity and branding.

During the four-year duration of the FRONTSH1P project, this document will be used and updated as required (contractually and otherwise). This communication and dissemination plan (CDP) details the process and the stages involved in the promotion and awareness raising of the project, including dissemination of information among the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and other target groups with the ability to contribute to the success of the project. It details the process for the delivery of information on the project, highlighting its relevance and effectiveness and the eventual results of each systemic solution.

2. Scope and Structure of the CDP

This CDP forms the basis for the overall communication management of the project, to which all project partners contribute. It is the main pillar for the dissemination aspect of the Dissemination and Exploitation work package (WP9). This communication and dissemination plan provides overall insight and a detailed overview on planned communication efforts and offers guidance for the efficient and timely implementation of the project.

As both the communication as well as the dissemination and exploitation aspects are mandatory requirements of H2020 projects, this CDP aims at planning and guiding communication in view of promoting the action and its results, “by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”. Tethered to communication activities and remaining distinct, dissemination means “sharing research results with potential users – peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers”.¹

In section 3 ‘About FRONTSH1P’, this CDP highlights the projects’ objectives and expected impact. Following section 3, section 4 ‘Communication and Dissemination Overview’ will delineate in detail communication objectives and messages, target groups and their segmentation, as well as communication tools. Section 5 ‘Evaluation Methods’ elaborates on monitoring the project’s communication and dissemination activities, on related indicators and KPI’s. In section 6 ‘Internal Communication’, the project’s coordination of communication and dissemination activities are explained, as well as its workflow and the rights and obligations that have to be taken into account. Finally, section 7 ‘Visual Identity & Branding’ presents the means that are being used to create a unique and easily recognisable project identity.

¹ European Commission, H2020 Online Manual:
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

3. About FRONTSH1P

3.1 Overall Objective

FRONTSH1P is funded under the Horizon 2020 framework programme. The project receives funds under call H2020-LC-GD-2020, thus responding to the issue of “building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal”. More specifically, the treated topic is the “demonstration of systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy”.

With this project, the consortium aims to boost circularity by providing systemic solutions, who will not least play a vital role in the recovery from the adverse socio-economic and environmental impacts of the COVID-19 crisis. Citizen needs will be put at the centre of the CSS's development, thereby ensuring just regional transition and thus environmental sustainability, the creation of new jobs and social inclusion. Furthermore, next to their demonstration in the Łódzkie region, the CSSs will be replicated in four other regions in Europe: Campania (Italy), Stereá Elláda (Greece), Região do Norte (Portugal), and Friesland (the Netherlands).

In sum: The overall objective of FRONTSH1P is to ensure the green and just transition of the Polish Łódzkie region towards decarbonization and territorial regeneration through the demonstration of four circular systemic solutions (TRL7), each in turn interconnected with one another and altogether tackling the regional challenges and opportunities identified in advance. Through their flexibility and modularity, the four CSSs guarantee high replicability and scalability to other territories across Europe and beyond, which will be demonstrated through the involvement of the above-mentioned four additional regions across Europe.

3.2 Specific Objectives

The main objective of FRONTSH1P is anchored around six specific objectives and associated quantified targets for the four CSSs.

The first objective concerns the deployment of a demonstration of the four circular systemic solutions in the Łódzkie region as the foundation for a successful and ambitious circular bio-economy transformation. The main targets are to reduce the transition timing, to allow for secondary raw materials and wastewater to be fully exploited, and to increase the

decarbonisation targets – all the while ensuring citizen engagement and proactive participation. A cross-cutting objective concerns the development of a circular governance model and the enabling of ICT solutions for all CSSs and the stakeholder's community as central pillar of the cluster. Namely: to develop a circular governance model and an operational approach for the territorial cluster; to develop a digital platform and decision support tools for data exchange and management; to develop regional circular booster toolkits; and to develop a specific tool for long-life learning activities made available through a dedicated e-learning platform.

The second objective regards the development of a replication plan based on mutual learning of the five committed regions, in turn based on a mix of the four CSSs, tools and methodologies. This will be a refinement of the initial replication plan to integrate technical solutions that are adapted to the local conditions and that involve local stakeholders while supporting the development of circular economic action plans in the regions with a long-term vision.

The third objective involves KPI assessment through a rigorous monitoring and evaluation programme that pays special attention to data collection, their regulation (GDPR), an indicator framework and their integration in a monitoring platform.

The fourth objective deals with the development of business models that are associated with the deployment of the CSSs, in order to foster the creation of a business ecosystem engaging large companies, SMEs, start-ups, farmers, citizens and public authorities alike.

The fifth objective regards the development of social inclusive programmes, that foster the market leverage of technological solutions and promote the creation of a socially inclusive ecosystem for the most vulnerable and marginalized citizens in both rural and urban areas.

The sixth and final objective concerns the deployment of a local and European/international communication and dissemination strategy, as this deliverable elaborates.

3.3 Expected Impact

The expected impact of FRONTSH1P is manifold. Concerning the decoupling of economic and human activities from the consumption of finite resources and the production of GHG emissions, FRONTSH1P will support the transition from fossil fuels to circular syngas, substitute fossil-based oils with circular biodegradable bio-lubricants, substitute char to avoid the use of energy and chemicals, and collect and valorise OFMSW (diverted from landfilling) – thereby ensuring the transition towards a more circular and climate-neutral economy.

FRONTSH1P will improve the sustainability and circularity of the regional clusters' economic sectors, their natural ecosystems, and the management and valorisation of local resources by reusing wood packaging as main material in the creation of furniture, by retrieving bioenergy, compost and bioplastics from urban and food industry waste, by creating products and wealth from abandoned marginal lands, thus revitalising them, by transforming wastewaters from a challenge to an opportunity, by extending the lifetimes of products through 3D printing and repair, and by utilising plastic waste in acoustic and thermal insulation foamed applications.

Regarding the creation of circular business opportunities and a structured pipeline of investment projects, FRONTSH1P estimates the revenues associated with the main products and services to be delivered for all actors involved in the Łódzkie region to account for a total turnover of about €190 m/y by 2030. Operational Investments (OPEX) have been estimated to amount for about €15,3 m/y, equally by 2030. In order to increase circular and climate-neutral practices among citizens and their participation in the systemic solutions, FRONTSH1P will implement a bottom-up approach for a tailored design of the CSSs according to citizen feedback and needs. Furthermore, the project aims to initially make 5,000 citizens (including high school students) in the Łódzkie region aware of the FRONTSH1P goals, who will then also be involved in a specific reward system, that is based on gamification methods and specifically tailored to different target groups.

Concerning the creation of new jobs in the short- to medium-term, FRONTSH1P has the ambitious goal to create and maintain up to 4,000 new jobs by 2030. It aims to achieve this through the launch of new economic activities in the clusters as well as by the inclusion of more vulnerable people in new socially relevant activities such as recycling and repairing schemes. Regarding the issue of a more effective development of circular solutions through knowledge transfer between territorial clusters funded under the same topic and other territories across EU member states and associated countries, FRONTSH1P will create a stakeholder network based on existing European networks, projects, and initiatives, which will become a powerful tool for knowledge transfer as to support replication across the EU and associated countries.

Lastly, FRONTSH1P objectives are well in line with the main targets set out in the European Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, Bioeconomy Strategy and Industrial Strategy and will develop an interregional cooperation model for circular economy projects in order to achieve a more effective and widespread uptake as well as an easier replication, scalability, and visibility of circular systemic solutions and hence the multiplication of economic, social, and environmental benefits to achieve the above-mentioned policy goals.

4. Communication and Dissemination Overview

4.1 Communication Objectives and Messages

4.1.1 General Objectives

Communication and dissemination activities in FRONTSH1P will promote the project's actions and outcomes, thereby paving the way for an effective exploitation of the project's results. Communication activities aim for two-way exchanges, guaranteeing not only that the project and its outcomes reach the segmented and targeted communication audiences, but also that the project receives valuable input from relevant stakeholders (government & policy makers, industry, academia & research community, citizens, and other EU projects & initiatives). Linking FRONTSH1P with relevant clusters and projects to ensure cooperation and learning will furthermore promote the long-term vision of the project. Thus, proper tailoring and targeted messaging is necessary to ensure the achievement of the objectives outlined in this CDP and carried out by WP9. The communication objectives and messages as defined by this section are underpinned by the FRONTSH1P project's core concepts.

1. Share the identified strengths and weaknesses, as well as their causes, of the Łódzkie region as it transitions towards a circular economy.
2. Generate interest for public and private investments that contribute to overcoming market failures in the areas covered by the implementation of the CSSs in the regions.
3. Improve consumers' and citizens' understanding and acceptance of circular and climate neutral services and products.
4. Collaborate with community-based innovation schemes in the areas of wood packaging, food & feed, water & nutrients, and plastic & rubber waste.
5. Detail sustainable and inclusive growth in the Łódzkie clusters as part of their socio-economic recovery from the Covid-19 crisis.

4.1.2 Key Messages

Arising from the aforementioned objectives, a collection of 'permanent key messages' can be defined. These form the basis for a deeper approach related to tailored messaging for target audiences. The messages can also be used to inspire and guide initial communication activities. As the project advances, these key messages are likely subject to change and adaptation.

4.1.2.1 Key Message 1

“FRONTSH1P project will contribute to building a low-carbon, climate resilient future by furthering the green and just transition of the Polish Łódzkie region towards decarbonization and territorial regeneration, thus contributing to the continuous transformation of the Łódzkie region to one of the leading European regions in the circular economy.”

4.1.2.2 Key Message 2

“Demonstration of the systemic solutions in the territory is a direct response to the challenges faced by the Łódzkie region, turning combating climate change into a possibility for economic growth and the creation of new jobs. FRONTSH1P outcomes will be incorporated in the Circular Economy Action Plan of the region, thus guaranteeing a long-lasting effect of the project.”

4.1.2.3 Key Message 3

“The FRONTSH1P approach is based on the creation of a Circular Governance Model that allows to exploit the project results beyond local boundaries, allowing a participatory, open, inclusive and socially innovative approach that includes all key stakeholders in the territories, aiding them to manage their transition towards circular value chains.”

4.1.2.4 Key Message 4

“The CSSs will be highly flexible and modular, guarantee a high replicability and scalability to other territories across Europe and beyond, enabling mutual learning with the projects partner regions and others to accelerate the European systemic circular transition, in turn guaranteeing a lasting impact of FRONTSH1P project.”

4.1.2.5 Key Message 5

“FRONTSH1P will develop business models associated to the deployment of the CSSs, thereby creating a business ecosystem engaging large companies, SMEs, start-ups, farmers, citizens and public authorities alike. This development will be accompanied by social inclusive programmes, which will guarantee the creation of a socially inclusive ecosystem for the most vulnerable and marginalized citizens.”

4.1.3 Specific Messages per Circular Systemic Solution

In addition to these general key messages, each CSS also has their own specific message(s) that they need to convey to the project's target audiences. As the project progresses, these messages will be further defined and finetuned.

4.1.3.1 Wood Packaging CSS Specific Messages

"The first CSS focuses on the valorisation of wood packaging waste through refurbishment, reuse, recycling, energy recovery, and material valorisation, thus creating a new value chain. Low quality wood and wooden residues will be gasified to produce heat through gas combustion, as well as char. Flue gases will be treated, and CO₂ captured (up to 80% efficiency of post-combustion capture and decrease in NO_x emission by > 20% obtained by CH₄/syngas cofiring). Char, pigment/filler, and CO₂ will in turn be used in the other three CSSs as compost, in the plastic industry, and in decarbonising foaming processes respectively."

4.1.3.2 Food & Feed CSS Specific Messages

"The second CSS aims to develop a CO₂ assisted pre-treatment of agro-industrial waste combined with biotechnological treatments for the obtaining of sugars and FFAs as component for foaming biomaterials, to establish innovative genotypes of oil crops (rapeseed, milk thistle) in marginal lands to obtain biodegradable bio-lubricants formulations, bio-oils for insulating materials and locally available animal feed, and to produce biobased building blocks (diols and dicarboxylic acids) from second generation feedstock (from regional agro-industrial waste) for the formulation of new compostable bioplastics for bags for separate OFMSW collection."

4.1.3.3 Water & Nutrients CSS Specific Messages

"The third CSS aims to further develop a compact wastewater management unit for nutrients extraction (P, N, K) from agricultural waste-waters and a bigger plant for municipal wastewater that both use microalgae, to produce circular bio-stimulants from wastewaters, and to close the water loop and recycle clean water."

4.1.3.4 Plastic & Rubber Waste CSS Specific Messages

"The fourth CSS aims to optimize a pyrolysis system for chlorinated compounds, to further develop a supercritical CO₂ expansion system for insulating biomaterials, and to demonstrate low-cost 3D printing for repairing of household appliances."

4.2 Target Groups

FRONTSH1P communication and dissemination activities are specifically aimed at making the project's results available to relevant target groups as soon as possible, in order to raise awareness of the proposed actions per CSS and to promote their adoption by the communities in which they are being implemented. The activities will also contribute to increase the visibility of the replication methods used in selected Italian, Greek, Portuguese, and Dutch regions as well as to promote them in other regions.

Different target groups will be the aim of the communication and dissemination activities, each requiring a distinct strategy using targeted messages, means and language. The table on the following page provides a visual representation of our initial mapping of target audiences, their definition and communication opportunities.

Table 1: Target Groups

Target Groups	Exemplification	Communication Channels
Government	Policy Makers at European, Regional and Local Level; EU Agencies and Institutions; Regional Development Agencies	Policy Recommendations; Project Publications; Policy Forums; Workshops; Conferences; Website; Newsletter Social Media; Digital Platform; Final Conference in Brussels
Academia	Universities; Research Institutions; Technology Centres; the Scientific Community; European Scientific Networks	Project Publications; Scientific Journals; Workshops; Conferences; Website; Newsletter; Social Media; Final Conference in Brussels
Private Sector	Industry (Large & SMEs); Agricultural Sector; Energy Sector; Chemical Sector; Residential Sector; European Industry Networks	Workshops; Conferences; Website; Newsletter; Social Media; Digital Platform; Final Conference in Brussels
Citizens	The General Public interested in the project; NGOs; European Associations; the Media	Project Publications; Press Releases; Promotional Material; Website; Newsletter; Social Media;

4.2.1 Target Group Segmentation

For communication to be effective and efficient, the above-mentioned target groups require a high degree of segmentation to allow for sufficient detailed granularity in communication and dissemination activities. Appropriate segmentation of the project audience is necessary as the interest of every group is different. Targeted Group segmentation will therefore cover all four defined target audiences and will further delineate these 'groups' into sub-target groups, according to their distinct needs and characteristics. These sub-target groups could in turn be further defined for the sake of achieving an optimal level of granularity. Additionally, each group is associated with a level of dissemination as to order and add a hierarchy to communication and dissemination.

The identified target audience segments will be further detailed in order to offer clear guidelines on how to tailor the project's communication efforts. As the project progresses, the following target groups are likely to be further segmented.

Figure 1: Target Groups

Policy Makers – European Level	
Description	Actors and bodies at European level working and engaged in EU policy making regarding policy domains relevant to FRONTSHIP project – circular economy, environment, and climate action; regional and economic development; research and innovation.
Communication Approach	Reporting about project outcomes; policy recommendations on existing barriers and key paths to boost circular economy.
Dissemination Level	Primary
Target Profiles	Audience EU Directorate-Generals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DG CLIMA • DG ENV • DG GROW • DG REGIO • DG RTD EU Agencies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EEA • EIT • CINEA • EISMEA • REA

Policy Makers – Regional & Local Level	
Description	Policy makers engaged in territorial (regional and local) government/authorities. At the regional and local level, the prime actors are those that are directly or indirectly involved with regional development policy (strategy and implementation). Beyond generalist profiles, this bracket also includes specialists as far as it relates to the projects main policy domains (circular economy, regional development, research and innovation).
Communication Approach	Report about project outcomes and provide segment specific communication that informs regional actors about the benefits and expected impact of the CSSs implementation and in general green transition (policy recommendations, summary publications, policy forums, etc.). Assessments of public supported policy and solutions.
Dissemination Level	Primary
Target Profiles	Audience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Łódzkie Region • Campania Region, • Stereá Elláda Region • Região do Norte • Friesland Region

Policy Makers – National Level	
Description	Policy makers working at the central government level. At the national level, the prime actors are those working directly on environmental, regional, and innovation policy.
Communication Approach	Report about project outcomes and raise awareness of the circular systemic solutions approach, as well as its benefits and impacts on the partner territories. Policy recommendations on existing barriers and key paths to boost circular economy.
Dissemination Level	Secondary
Target Audience Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government of Poland • Government of Italy • Government of Greece • Government of Portugal • Government of the Netherlands

Regional Development Agencies	
Description	RDA stakeholders are actors and individuals operating at regional level in regional government agencies for territorial and economic development. These actors are of central importance for their proximity to other local and regional stakeholders.
Communication Approach	Networking and clustering approaches (workshops, conferences, etc.) to inform about FRONTSHIP and to actively seek cooperation and exchange. EURADA, as umbrella organisation of European development agencies will facilitate exchange between the project consortium and European and non-European RDAs.
Dissemination Level	Secondary
Target Audience Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Regional Development Agencies

Academia Stakeholders		
Description	Members of the scientific community engaged with the fields of the project's systemic solutions. Including individuals, institutions, and networks.	
Communication Approach	Openly inform and raise awareness about FRONTSH1P project, its ambition, progress, outcomes, and expected impacts on the territories through online media, project partner networks and scientific publications. Seek exchange and participation through organisation and participation of conferences, workshops, and other events. Provision of papers and data to help increasing the knowledge on circular economy.	
Dissemination Level	Primary	
Target Audience Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities • Research Institutions • Technology Centres • European Networks (e.g., European Circular Economy Stakeholders Platform, European Energy Research Alliance)	

Industry Stakeholder		
Description	Large Companies, SMEs, Farmers and Investors.	
Communication Approach	Inform and raise awareness about FRONTSH1P project, its guiding ideas, outcomes, and expected impacts. Clear overview of what works well and what does not, as well as development of plans for investment and upscaling. Provision of reports on both financing and business plans.	
Dissemination Level	Primary	
Target Audience Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local/Regional SMEs • International Companies • Agricultural Sector • Energy Sector • Chemical Sector • Residential Sector • European Industry Networks (e.g., Bio-Based Industries Consortium, European Bioplastics, Enterprise Europe Network)	

General Public	
Description	Includes all lay people not coming from academia, government, or administration, as well as other interested parties.
Communication Approach	Increase public awareness of the project's objectives, activities and eventual impact, as well as its faced challenges and opportunities. Provide tangible results about circular economy approaches, success stories and the rationale for engagement, as well as contribution options to make it possible. Training offers (workshops, etc.) for seizing the benefits of the circular economy.
Dissemination Level	Secondary
Target Audience Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens

In addition to these segmented target groups, a network of stakeholders (at least 140 members) will be identified and established during FRONTSH1P. This network will then be used to further disseminate the project results and to increase the project's impact. Moreover, the network will provide overall insight into the findings of the four deployed CSSs and give their opinion on the developed replication strategies in the partner regions. The active participation of the stakeholder network will be ensured through open lines of communication and constant updates provided by the various communication tools used by the project.

4.3 Communication Instruments

The variety of segmented target groups requires the use of multiple intersecting tools and channels in FRONTSH1P project in order to effectively inform, communicate, and engage stakeholder, audiences, and target groups. As to fully and effectively reach all target groups delineated within the preceding section, FRONTSH1P will use a mix of tools and channels that will periodically be reviewed for their efficacy and impact. Due to the lasting restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic, online tools take even greater precedence than ever before.

Communication is essential to ensure that a high impact is achieved as far as the project's activities and results are concerned. Communication towards target groups will thus enjoy priority attention for FRONTSH1P. Effective action in this respect will ensure that the project reaches out to the largest pool of policy makers, members of the scientific community, representatives of the public sector and citizens. Well-crafted messages as part of

communication activities will contribute to the promotion of the economic and societal benefits of the developed circular systemic solutions to the wider public.

Communication started with M1 in November 2021 and the launch of the project's website and first social media channels. Effective social media and other communication for FRONTSH1P will continuously accelerate and augment in the first months of the project. The first newsletter will be published at the end of M3 in January 2022. A first promotional video has been released. First events will be soon after attended and organised. The launch of the e-learning platform is foreseen for the second or third year of the project. The last dissemination activity will be the final event in Brussels at the end of the project.

4.3.1 Tools

The communication tools that are at the disposal of the project are detailed below with their associated KPIs being detailed in section 5 of this CDP. It must be noted that the project's communication and dissemination activities and its engagement with the target audiences is not limited to the project's own channels. Communication tools and channels for dissemination within the project partners' organisations will additionally be sought.

4.3.1.1 Website

The project website, available at www.frontsh1p.eu and/or www.frontship.eu, is one of the main communication and dissemination tools of FRONTSH1P. The website can address a wide range of stakeholders who can easily access relevant information specific to their needs and interests. Concerning content, the website contains most of the important information about the project and will be frequently updated and expanded. All public reports created will be published on the FRONTSH1P website.

The landing page of the project website is currently launched with a user-friendly design, so that the visitor can immediately get an overview of the project's scope, with the usage of images and short written contents. Furthermore, the website contains a 'partners' section, containing short descriptions of each member of the consortium with links to their own respective websites, and a contact section, containing the contact details of EURADA, the project's communication manager. All content and published material will be written in English and most of this content will be prepared with little technical language aiming to ensure that the message can reach a wide range of audiences. It will be updated with a more detailed presentation of the project's activities and its financing institutions and programmes.

Further website sections currently foreseen are a 'News' section, a 'Events' section, including a regularly updated event calendar that will promote public events such as seminars and

workshops aiming for face-to-face engagement with different stakeholders, a 'Results' section, a 'Regions' section, providing information about the five partner regions of the project, and a possibility to subscribe to the project's newsletter and a message box, offering the possibility to easily get in contact with the project consortium.

Special attention will be paid to the implementation of good practices related with Search Engine Optimisation (SEO), allowing the project to reach a wider range of stakeholders with a SEO-friendly website. Considering the nature of the project, a particular focus will be placed on on-page SEO practices, that involves creating and optimising HTML tag like titles and meta descriptions to rank higher in search engines and consequently to become more visible to the relevant users. SEO practices will be implemented in compliance with search intent, which means that the content produced – type, format, angle – needs to address the information users are expected to find. More specifically, technical on-page optimizations that will be used by the project's communication manager are listed below:

- Short and descriptive URL slug, anticipating the page's content before visiting it;
- Inclusion of target keywords in titles;
- Addition of meta descriptions: HTML code meant to briefly summarise the page;
- Addition of internal links to and from the website pages, in order to pass link authority to other relevant pages and help search engine understand page content;
- Optimization of images by naming them appropriately, using descriptive ALT TEXT and compressing image size;
- Optimization of content for readability by writing short sentences and paragraphs, using descriptive subheadings and a large font;
- Use of open graph (OG) meta tags to customise titles' descriptions when pages are shared on social media;
- Exploitation of link building to build relationship with other relevant site owners based on relevance, relation, and value exchange.

4.3.1.2 Partner Websites

In line with the large scale of the project, all partners will use their own websites to promote the general awareness about FRONTSHIP, namely in the areas in which they are engaged. It is recommended that specific pages detailing work undertaken in the framework of FRONTSHIP use a design that is similar to the visual design of the project (colours and images). Through the individual partner' websites, all partners will make use of their own networks of stakeholders to communicate and disseminate the project, its activities, and the achieved results, thus contributing to the establishment of the envisioned stakeholder network.

4.3.1.3 Social Media

The project's presence on social media, particularly Twitter and LinkedIn, will maximise the communication and dissemination impact of the project and use these channels to reach a wide range of potential stakeholders. All target groups will be the objective of social media activities.

The content that is published on the social media channels first reflects updates on the project status and the publication of project deliverables and publications, as well as in general news on FRONTSH1P.

Advertisement of upcoming events and meetings, including those organised by members of the project consortium, those in which one or more partners are participating, and those related to the topic of the project without direct project participation will be done via the project's social media channels.

Useful content from other European circular economy projects and initiatives, such as articles, academic papers, and tools for implementing circular systemic solutions will be shared, in order to create an amplifier effect and contribute to increasing the broader visibility of European circular economy activities.

A Dissemination and Replication Team (DRT) with a designated responsible for communication from each WP leader has been established. EURADA coordinates the team and acts as a community manager of the social media channels of the project. The EURADA communication expert requests content and updates from each member to ensure there is a regular and timely distribution of content to post on the different social networks.

Furthermore, EURADA is responsible for providing social media posts to the consortium in order to facilitate the project's regular updates on the partners' social media accounts, thus reaching a wider audience.

The following accounts have thus far been created:

- Twitter: @frontsh1p
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/frontsh1p/>
- YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC_fwujmMubqvtreoKnmEQdg

FRONTSH1P's Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have been launched in November 2021 and will be the main focus of the project's social media activities. FRONTSH1P's YouTube Account has also already been launched in December 2021 and will serve as publication platform for promotional videos. Furthermore, the creation of an Instagram account is equally foreseen.

4.3.1.4 Promotional Videos

Professionally filmed and edited promotional videos that draw on footage from consortium meetings and potentially other meaningful material will be created to present the project, the partners and their activities. They will be uploaded on the YouTube channel of the project and those of the project partners, as well as linked both on the project website and the partner websites. The videos will also be shown at conferences and other events project partners attend.

The first video has already been published: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f0htes4G8aE>

4.3.1.5 Newsletter

FRONTSH1P will publish and disseminate its achieved results through a newsletter. The newsletter will follow a recurring template and structure, except when in need of deviation. The project newsletter is one of the project's main communication tools for regular dissemination of information reaching key stakeholders. The newsletter covers ongoing project activities and outputs from recent activities (reports, event and workshop outcomes, WP results, etc.). It will also focus on special topics defined by the consortium and that are relevant to the target audiences. Each issue of the newsletter will initially be emailed out to a mailing list comprised of addresses that signed up for it. It is then made available on the project's website and social media channels to allow those who did not yet sign up to the mailing list in time to access it.

The target audience is comprised of all identified target groups and all those otherwise interested in the project's outcomes. The FRONTSH1P newsletter will initially be released at quarterly intervals, with a potential rescheduling at a later point in time. EURADA coordinates the production and electronic dissemination of the newsletter and seeks to acquire content from each partner to ensure accuracy of information and highlighting deliverables or activities that are being created at the time of publication. The dissemination is carried out using the mailing list software Mailchimp.

As far as the structuring of the newsletter is concerned, there will be a short description of each article provided, containing a link to the full articles which are always hosted on the project's website. This way each article is simply available by visiting the relevant section of the website ('News'). The newsletter itself is also made available on a dedicated sub-section of the website ('Newsletter'), which allows visitors to select a particular newsletter edition

and view in their browser the content of the email which has been sent out. Registration to the newsletter is accessible through the project website.

The newsletter will be compliant with the European GDPR. EURADA will create a clear distribution list for project communication and dissemination as far as the newsletter is concerned. Each partner will be requested to contact their stakeholder networks and to invite them to subscribe to the newsletter in order to increase the projects outreach. Regular calls will also be made, through social media, publications and news articles that encourage subscription.

As far as the newsletter's workflow is concerned within the project, EURADA will manage and import the distribution list on its Mailchimp account. EURADA will maintain all collected information only for the duration of the project. At the end of the project, EURADA will delete the amassed data from its Mailchimp account and will delete the newsletters already sent as to no data will remain in the system to comply with data regulation.

4.3.1.6 Press Releases, Press Conferences, and other Media Coverage

Press releases will be issued by all partners during the project coinciding with important milestones such as local or European events, publication releases or the launch of the project's platforms. All press releases will be made available on the project's website. Press conferences will be held when advisable, such as during the project's kick-off meeting. The consortium will actively seek to publish articles in publication outlets such as technical magazines. Furthermore, opportunities for interviews (radio, podcasts, and newspapers) will be actively sought.

4.3.1.7 Conferences, Workshops and other Events

In order to engage citizens, researchers and practitioners beyond online media and to link them to FRONTSH1P, thus creating a stakeholder network, the consortium will continuously organise events, such as conferences and workshops, during the course of the project. The academia partners of the consortium will play a key role in this activity, enabling close exchange with the relevant scientific community concerned with the key issues faced by FRONTSH1P. Another goal of these events is the clustering with other relevant projects in the field of circular economy in order to ensure close cooperation and to develop synergies and mutual activities (especially with the CCRI). Professionally developed branded materials, including posters and flyers, will be created and supplied for use and distribution. The project partners will organise and participate in at least 20 events during the lifetime of the project, aimed at citizens, scientists and practitioners alike.

4.3.1.8 E-Learning Platform

An e-learning platform will be developed using gamification methods (quizzes, leagues, digital badges, etc.), with high accessibility to support people with disabilities and to guarantee easy access on mobile devices, building upon the technical skills of the consortium (IT bandwidth and access, etc.).

4.3.1.9 Final Event in Brussels

A final dissemination event involving all stakeholders as active participants will be organised at the end of the project. It will be a high-level international event focused on summarising the project outcomes towards a wide international audience: EU officers, regional and national institutions, enterprises, research institutions, and citizens, thus encouraging further dialogue and networking. The event programme will include thematic workshops featuring operational teams coordinated by experts.

4.3.2 Editorial Plan

The frequency of communication and dissemination content deliverables varies according to the different activities. While it is envisioned to post on social media at the least weekly, especially in the later phases of the project when more results will be readily available for dissemination, the newsletter will be published quarterly and the frequency of press releases will vary according to reached projects milestones. To ensure a constant online presence, the project's communication manager will also endeavour to draw on relevant third-party content.

5. Evaluation Methods

5.1 Monitoring

The main objective here is to ensure a high-quality communication strategy execution. It is important that this evaluation is carried out on a continuous basis to guarantee:

- An effective impact assessment and update or redefinition of communication activities;
- A high quality of the communication activities carried out.

The execution of this plan will be measured through the following indicators:

- Analytics related to the FRONTSH1P website and its social media accounts interests (google analytics for the website and the analytics provided by the respective social media platforms, i.e., Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, Instagram). A careful monitoring of FRONTSH1P's online hits will be done together with an analysis of the impact of activities (e.g., publication of a new article). The consortium uses web tools for analysing visitor traffic, giving a complete picture on the number of visitors, visited pages, geographical coverage, as well as origin and activities of visitors, revealing the audience's needs and;
- Number of subscribers to the project's newsletter;
- Number of organised events and attendants;
- Number of news articles and interviews;
- Number of views of the project videos.

5.2 Communication and Dissemination Indicators and Reporting

To facilitate an accurate monitoring and assessment of the communication and dissemination activities and to understand the impact of the actions carried out, it is necessary for all partners to register the activities that they implement. In this sense a section to report every communication activity or publication (articles, social media posts, attended events, etc.) will be available on the project's internal platform. Each consortium member will be required to record here their activities at regular intervals.

The indicators that will be reported are as follows:

- Number of visits to frontsh1p.eu;
- Accumulated number of followers on social media;

- Accumulated number of subscribers to the project newsletter;
- Accumulated number of press releases distributed;
- Accumulated number of articles published on external media;
- Accumulated number of participants in conferences and workshops;
- Accumulated number of relevant events on which project partners participated.

Therefore:

- All partners will respect the communication guidelines set out in this document;
- All partners will register their communication activities in the communication reporting document;
- All partners will need to save evidence of the activities carried out.

By regular monitoring communication and dissemination activities, it is possible to assess whether the CDP implementation is appropriate and it will enable the consortium to see which activities had the biggest impact on the relevant stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms). Conclusions from this monitoring will affect updates of the CDP.

5.3 Communication and Dissemination KPIs

To measure communication and dissemination progress and impact, quantifiable KPIs are enumerated below. The values in the following table state the number of interactions with project stakeholders that the project seeks for each of the listed activities.

Table 2: Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total
Newsletter Subscribers	250	250	250	250	1,000
Website Visits	6,250	6,250	6,250	6,250	25,000
Social Media Followers (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube & Instagram)	1,250	1,250	1,250	1,250	5,000
Media Coverage	2 News Articles & 2 Interviews, reaching at least 2,500 professionals and practitioners	2 News Articles & 2 Interviews, reaching at least 2,500 professionals and practitioners	2 News Articles & 2 Interviews, reaching at least 2,500 professionals and practitioners	2 News Articles & 2 Interviews, reaching at least 2,500 professionals and practitioners	8 News Articles & 8 Interviews, reaching at least 10,000 professionals and practitioners
Video Views	1,250	1,250	1,250	1,250	5,000
Organised Events	5, reaching at least 750 scientists, citizens and practitioners	5, reaching at least 750 scientists, citizens and practitioners	5, reaching at least 750 scientists, citizens and practitioners	5, reaching at least 750 scientists, citizens and practitioners	20, reaching at least 3000 scientists, citizens and practitioners

6. Internal Communication

This section seeks to guide the internal communication and dissemination of FRONTSH1P. In order to effectively plan, share and coordinate efforts in a project with 34 partners, FRONTSH1P envisions a set of coordination and responsibilities guidelines in terms of internal communication, partner responsibility and obligations.

6.1 Coordination

Good communication among the project partners is key to the project success. A well-organised internal communication is furthermore crucial for the achievement of the objectives of WP9. It is also critical to make these processes as efficient as possible.

The project partners will be in permanent exchange with each other, through regular calls, e-mail (multiple mailing lists, depending on the tasks and needs), and meetings, thereby making sure that all members of the consortium play an active part in FRONTSH1P. To this end, interim reports will be asked of each project partner every six months.

To ensure proper capture of central results and their impact, the dissemination and replication team was set up, with EURADA being the member that will be chairing all meetings of it, therefore also being of charge of coordinating communication and dissemination activities. The DRT consists of the coordinator and all partners that will work at cluster level supporting the development and implementation of dissemination and replication of the project, but at least all WP leaders. The DRT will also provide additional periodic reports (in addition to the above-mentioned) in order to make a suitable supervising of critical communication and dissemination activities viable. The DRT will meet on a regular basis to discuss communication and dissemination activities and if necessary to steer them in a different direction. The frequency is envisioned to be every two to four weeks.

The DRT is formed by three different bodies:

- The Communication and Dissemination Secretariat (CDS) constitutes the central office coordinating all contacts towards stakeholder communities and other communication and dissemination audiences, including the media. CDS will be managed by EURADA with the assistance of the project coordinator and the WP leaders.
- The Clusters Collaboration Secretariat (CCS) will take care of the definition of the roadmap for the collaborative activities of FRONTSH1P with other projects and

clusters, in coordination with the CCRI office. The CCS will be managed by EURADA and supported by the project coordinator.

- The Exploitation & Innovation Leader.

STAM is furthermore entrusted with the creation of the common platform and workspace for the project consortium that is based on the collaboration software Confluence.

All partners will identify and signal at least 1 communication representative, who holds the responsibility for the activities at a project partner level and reporting, and who serves as central contact person for all communication and dissemination matters. From the side of the communication manager, an email address was created for aggregating communication tasks within WP9's lead beneficiary: frontsh1p@eurada.org.

Table 3: Communication and Dissemination Coordination

Partner	Role in Communication and Dissemination Activities
Coordinator	<p>As project coordinator, K-FLEX will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support EURADA by identifying and providing key project results. • Monitor that there is a continuous active contribution from all project partners to communication and dissemination activities; • Ensure a timely and effective communication within the consortium and between the consortium and the EC; • Manage external stakeholder communication supporting EURADA; • Supervise and coordinate the organisation and implementation of scientific and dissemination events.
EURADA	<p>As lead beneficiary of the communication and dissemination work package, EURADA will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate the project and its results at project level and involve stakeholders ensuring activities are sustainable and impactful; • Manage the project's website and social media platforms; • Produce content for the website and social media platforms; • Inform project partners with relevant information that supports partners' efforts in communication and dissemination activities; • Produce newsletters, manage press office duties, etc; • Manage the creation of the e-learning platform;
WP Leader	<p>The work package leaders will aid the communication manager by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting in the content creation related to the WPs; • Supporting in the content creation of press releases and other joint publications of the consortium; • Identifying relevant conferences and other events; • Updating EURADA regularly about WP activities and outcomes.

6.2 Workflow

The following workflow relates to the communication and dissemination channels of FRONTSH1P: website; social media; video; newsletter; press releases; project newsletter; branded materials (posters, flyers, etc.).

WP9 is led by EURADA. Although communication and dissemination activities are channelled through specific team members, all partners are responsible for creating content to be published in a synchronised and strategic manner. EURADA will edit and review all content provided by the project partners to be published via the project's own distribution channels to guarantee that the content will be harmonious and easily recognisable as FRONTSH1P content.

Communication and dissemination activities will be monitored and coordinated by EURADA. All FRONTSH1P related social media content production and publication should reach EURADA. The 'where' and 'when' of the project communication and dissemination is very important.

6.3 Rights and Obligations

As stated in the Grant Agreement (GA), all beneficiaries of the project must as soon as possible, sole exception being when it goes against their legitimate interests, disseminate the project's results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, including scientific publications.

Furthermore, each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action, the beneficiaries must deposit it in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the following: the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications; other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the data management plan; provide information (via the repository) about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and, where possible, provide the tools and instruments themselves).

Any dissemination of results must, unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, display the EU emblem and include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037031”.

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

7. Visual Identity & Branding

The visual identity is the graphical outlook and branding of the project. It differentiates FRONTSH1P from other similar projects and sets its style and graphics to be used.

7.1 Logo & CSS Branding

FRONTSH1P project recalls the word Łódź, which means ship in Polish. The consortium has thus agreed to use a ship as symbol in the logo to communicate graphically the basic principle behind the project: the transition and thus shipping towards a new paradigm of circular (bio)economy led by the Łódzkie region across Europe.

Figure 2: Project Logos

Each CSS is associated with a specific colour, making each CSS distinct and easily recognisable.

Figure 3: CSSs Colour Branding

7.2 Fonts

FRONTSH1P uses three fonts in its templates and its communication and dissemination activities:

- “Bureau” for ppt-titles and the logos
- “Nunito” for texts

7.3 Colours

FRONTSH1P uses the following colours for its logo and general branding:

Figure 4: Logos Colour Codes

The colour codes corresponding to the four CSSs are:

Figure 5: CSSs Colour Codes

7.4 Examples of Visual Identity and Branding

Figure 6: PPT Template Title Slide

Figure 7: Brandbook Extract

